

WINSENT – wind science and engineering test site in complex terrain, Germany

General description of the research facility and the research wind turbines

WINSENT¹, the test facility of the southern German wind energy research cluster WindForS², focuses on research questions in complex terrain. It is built and operated by the WindForS member ZSW³. Alongside technological developments, the WINSENT test site supports answering questions regarding social acceptance of wind energy and to align wind energy with nature conservation.

WINSENT consists of two accessible, open-source, modifiable research wind turbines, four meteorological masts of 100 m height and several measurement instruments, located in the surroundings. The two turbines have hub heights of 72 m, a rotor diameter of 50 m and thus an overall height of almost 100 m. Each turbine has a rated electrical output of 750 kW and features variable-speed operation and independently controlled pitch motors.

The turbine size still allows transferring knowledge of parameters such as loads, controller settings and turbine behaviour to larger wind turbines as different validated simulation models with varying degrees of detail (digital twins) exist. The turbines have been installed in a side-by-side configuration to enable the comparison of the behaviours of the modified turbine and the reference turbine. The met masts are positioned in front of and behind each research turbine. The masts are equipped with various meteorological sensors as well as with bat microphones, bird detection cameras and insect

¹ www.winsent.de

² www.windfors.de

³ www.zsw-bw.de/en

photo traps. The top anemometers of the masts are as high as the top blade tip position of the turbines.

Location of WINSENT test site

The WINSENT test site is located in the Swabian Alb⁴ about 70 km east of Stuttgart near the municipalities Geislingen an der Steige and Donzdorf in the federal state of Baden-Württemberg. The location on a forest-free plateau near a steep slope, the so-called Albtrauf, was defined and finally found in the course of a previous research project. Due to the steep slope, the turbines are exposed to inclined flow and high turbulence.

Figure 1. Illustration of test site layout: two research wind turbines in forest-free terrain near a slope and meteorological masts upstream and downstream [source: TUM-LAREG].

Control and measurement systems and signals

The measurement equipment consists of four meteorological masts, synchronized long-range scanning lidar systems, eddy-covariance systems, a ceilometer, a bird radar and bat detection microphones.

Numerical models of simple aero-elastic codes up to FSI-coupled or multi body codes of the research turbines have been developed by WindForS partners. A new baseline wind turbine controller has been developed which will be open to any research institution together with an OpenFAST model of the research wind turbines after a validation phase. The turbines are of open-access and have modifications to facilitate the work of researchers. They are extensively instrumented with sensors to capture mechanical load data from the tower bottom to the blade tip, monitor key operational parameters and record seismic vibrations in the surrounding environment.

Research possibilities

The test site is intended to be used to prepare, test and validate new technologies for example in the fields of turbine control, aerodynamics, operational management, measuring instruments and techniques, and monitoring. For the development and validation of simulation tools used in wind turbine system design, for designing single components and for modelling environmental influences (flow wind field etc.) measurement data is essential. The measurement data obtained from the

⁴ www.swabianalb.info

research turbines and the meteorological masts will be stored in a research data base. 10-min average data from the met masts as well as high-resolution turbine load data from selected operational cases will be made publicly accessible. Further data will be accessible for R&D activities upon request.

On account of the topological and topographical location, basic research on meteorological conditions with a view to wind energy use in complex-mountainous terrain is also envisaged. Icing (turbine loading, reduction in yield, testing of icing detectors etc.) and the increased number of lightning strokes should also be mentioned here. Moreover, mesoscale and microscale wind field modelling for complex terrain is not yet fully developed. It can be used for forecasting wind yields from current weather data (short-term prognosis) and thus improve yield prognoses for complex terrain. Accurate forecasting systems are also essential for the optimal design and operation of storage technologies and hybrid power plants.

The WINSENT test site is available for use for nature conservation research, with a focus on studies of birds and bats. The test site enables the development and validation of mitigation measures for birds and bats, while also contributing to closing knowledge gaps regarding animal behaviour in proximity to wind turbines.

For these reasons red kites have been fitted with GPS transmitters to continuously monitor and evaluate their movements. In parallel, a bird radar device was installed to continuously monitor the airspace of the test site for bird movements. By using a combination of the movement data with the comprehensive meteorological data collected at the test site such as wind speed, temperature, visibility, etc. correlations of bird activity with these parameters can be studied. Bat activity is continuously acoustically recorded at all four met masts and at the wind turbines at four different heights and combined with the meteorological data to study any possible further development of switch-off algorithms.

The test site offers the opportunity to test and to validate anti-collision systems that are to be used to protect bird species that are sensitive to wind power. Three systems have been validated already during the last two years by the use of laser-range finder measurements, ornithologists and the GPS fitted red kites.

Contact data and more information

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